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Atypical Idiopathic Intracranial Hypertension with Normal Cerebrospinal Fluid Pressure in a Child

Abstract

Idiopathic intracranial hypertension (IIH) is classically defined by raised intracranial pressure with normal neuroimaging and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) composition. However, atypical presentations where one diagnostic criterion is absent, such as normal CSF opening pressure, have been described. We report a pediatric case of probable IIH presenting with papilloedema and normal CSF pressure, underscoring the need for clinical vigilance and prompt management to prevent visual loss.

Case Report

A 10-year-old boy presented with a 5-month history of episodic moderate-intensity headache and occasional visual blurring. There were no episodes of tinnitus or diplopia. General neurological examination was unremarkable. Fundoscopic evaluation revealed bilateral grade 2 papilloedema, confirmed independently by two senior ophthalmologists.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain and magnetic resonance venography (MRV) were unremarkable, with no evidence of mass lesions, hydrocephalus, or venous sinus thrombosis. A lumbar puncture demonstrated normal CSF opening pressure, and CSF composition was within normal limits. These findings did not meet the classic IIH criteria that require elevated CSF pressure; nonetheless, the presence of unequivocal papilloedema and compatible symptoms raised strong suspicion for an atypical IIH variant (probable IIH with normal pressure) as described in the literature.

In view of the significant risk of progressive visual impairment, the patient was initiated on acetazolamide therapy with close ophthalmological and neurological follow-up. The frequency of headaches decreased over subsequent weeks, and no deterioration in visual symptoms was observed.

Discussion

Established diagnostic criteria for IIH typically include papilloedema, elevated CSF opening pressure, and exclusion of secondary causes on neuroimaging. Atypical presentations in which CSF opening pressure is within normal limits have been documented, suggesting that strict adherence to pressure thresholds may overlook clinically relevant cases. In such scenarios, papilloedema with suggestive symptoms and no alternative etiology warrants consideration of IIH and prompt treatment to protect vision, even in the absence of elevated measured pressure.

Conclusion

IIH should be considered in patients presenting with papilloedema and typical symptoms, even if CSF opening pressure is normal. Recognition of atypical presentations and early therapeutic intervention, such as acetazolamide, can be crucial in preserving vision.

Key References

1. Magesh P, Sendil Kumar A, Prabhuraman K. Idiopathic intracranial hypertension or pseudotumour cerebri? The conundrum of nomenclature in the presence of normal cerebrospinal fluid pressures. *IP Indian Journal of Anatomy and Surgery of Head, Neck and Brain*. 2018;4:106–110.
2. Foska A, Palaiodimou L, Stefanou MI, et al. Telltale signs of idiopathic intracranial hypertension with normal opening cerebrospinal fluid pressure. *Neurohospitalist*. 2022;13:103–106.